

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Influence of demographic analysis and job demand projections on recruitment effectiveness in colleges of education in delta state

Margret Nkechi OSAMOR * and Racheal Ejimevbo ONOYAKE

Department of Educational Management and Foundations, Delta State University, Abraka.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 28(01), 1379-1387

Publication history: Received on 25 August 2025; revised on 10 October 2025; accepted on 13 October 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.28.1.3405>

Abstract

This study examined the influence of demographic analysis and job demand projections on recruitment effectiveness in colleges of education in Delta State. It was guided by three research questions and one hypothesis. To examine the study, a descriptive and correlational method of the ex-post-facto research design was adopted. The population comprised 312 academic and senior non-academic staff involved in recruitment across the three public Colleges of Education in the state. Using stratified random sampling, a sample of 174 respondents was selected to ensure adequate representation across institutions and staff categories. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled "Demographic and Job Demand Recruitment Effectiveness Questionnaire (DJDREQ)". Face and content validity were established through expert review, while a pilot test conducted in a similar institution yielded a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.872, indicating high internal consistency. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and coefficient of determination for the research questions, while multiple regression analysis was used to test hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. Finding revealed that to a large extent demographic analysis of applicants influence the recruitment decisions in Colleges of Education in Delta State with an overall mean of 4.00. It was also discovered that there is a significant relationship between the consideration of demographic analysis, job demand projections, and the perceived effectiveness of recruitment practices in Colleges of Education in Delta State. It was recommended among others that Colleges of Education should formalize the use of demographic data and job demand projections in their recruitment policies to ensure equitable and strategically aligned hiring practices.

Keywords: Demographic Analysis; Job Demand Projections; Recruitment Effectiveness; Colleges of Education; Delta State

1. Introduction

The quality of education within any nation is significantly dependent on the caliber of its teachers, and this is particularly true for Colleges of Education, which bear the crucial responsibility of training future educators (Okwelle, & Deebom, 2009). In Nigeria, the recruitment of qualified teachers has been fraught with challenges, encompassing issues related to the quality of candidates, the sheer number of teachers needed, and the equitable distribution of educators across different regions (Aluede, Omoregie, & Aluede, 2020). Delta State, with its own unique socio-economic and geographical context, faces specific hurdles in ensuring its Colleges of Education can attract and retain the best academic talent (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). The effectiveness of recruitment in these institutions is paramount, as it directly influences the quality of teacher training and subsequently impacts the educational experiences of students throughout the state. Understanding the demographic profile of potential applicants, encompassing factors such as age, gender, experience, and qualifications, can significantly inform the development of targeted and effective recruitment strategies (Kotler & Armstrong, 2001). Analyzing these characteristics can reveal trends within the applicant pool, allowing institutions to tailor their outreach efforts and messaging to attract a diverse and qualified workforce (Olorunfoba &

* Corresponding author: OSAMOR, Margret Nkechi

Ajayi, 2006). Furthermore, research suggests a potential link between certain demographic factors and job performance or retention within educational settings, making demographic analysis a valuable tool for building a stable and effective staff (Maimuna, 2017).

Recruitment effectiveness in Colleges of Education is closely linked to demographic analysis and job demand projections, as these provide insights into workforce stability, productivity, and future institutional needs. Nkedishu (2020) highlighted that job security plays a critical role in shaping workers' productivity in educational centres, underscoring the importance of aligning recruitment strategies with long-term staffing sustainability. Similarly, Nkedishu (2022) emphasized that administrative efficiencies are central to improving teachers' productivity, suggesting that effective recruitment must consider not only staffing numbers but also organizational structures that enhance performance. Furthermore, Nkedishu, Nwaorgu, and Egwunyenga (2022) demonstrated how instructors' proficiency and the adoption of emerging technologies influence teaching effectiveness, implying that recruitment must strategically target candidates with the demographic and skill profiles necessary to meet evolving job demands in the education sector.

In addition to understanding who is applying, it is equally crucial for Colleges of Education to anticipate the future needs of the education sector by considering job demand projections for teachers in specific subject areas and educational levels (Carver-Thomas & Darling-Hammond, 2019). Aligning recruitment efforts with these projections ensures that colleges are recruiting staff who can effectively train teachers in high-need areas, thereby contributing to meeting the overall educational demands of Delta State (Ejumode, 2011). This proactive approach not only addresses potential teacher shortages but can also inform the enrollment and program offerings of the Colleges of Education themselves (Ekwoaba, Ikeije, & Ufoma, 2015). This seminar paper aims to investigate the influence of both demographic analysis and job demand projections on the effectiveness of recruitment practices within Colleges of Education in Delta State.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Colleges of Education in Delta State encounter considerable difficulties in their efforts to attract and recruit highly qualified academic staff (Ejumode, 2011). These challenges may arise from various factors, including the perceived attractiveness of academic careers within these institutions, competition from other sectors for skilled professionals, and the limitations of available institutional resources. Furthermore, there is a potential for mismatches to occur between the demographic profile of the academic staff recruited and the evolving needs of the colleges or the diverse student population they serve. For instance, an aging staff might lack the expertise to train future teachers on the latest educational technologies, while a lack of gender or ethnic diversity among staff could limit the range of perspectives and experiences offered to students.

A significant concern also exists regarding the alignment of recruitment practices with the projected demands for teachers in Delta State. Failure to adequately consider these projections can lead to critical shortages of qualified teachers in essential subject areas, such as science and mathematics, while potentially resulting in an oversupply of teachers in fields with limited employment opportunities. This misalignment not only creates inefficiencies within the education system but can also impede the state's broader human capital development goals. Traditional recruitment methods that may still be prevalent in some Colleges of Education in Delta State might no longer be sufficient to attract the most suitable candidates in the current competitive system. Relying solely on conventional approaches could limit the reach of recruitment efforts and fail to engage a diverse pool of potentially highly qualified individuals who might be more effectively reached through modern, targeted strategies. Therefore, a comprehensive examination of how demographic analysis and job demand projections currently utilized, and their impact on recruitment effectiveness, is warranted to inform improvements in the recruitment processes of Colleges of Education in Delta State. Thus, the following questions were raised;

- To what extent does the demographic analysis of applicants influence the recruitment decisions in Colleges of Education in Delta State?
- How do job demand projections for staff in Delta State impact the recruitment strategies employed by Colleges of Education?
- What is the relationship between the consideration of demographic analysis, job demand projections, and the perceived effectiveness of recruitment practices in Colleges of Education in Delta State?

1.2. Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between the consideration of demographic analysis, job demand projections, and the perceived effectiveness of recruitment practices in Colleges of Education in Delta State.

2. Literature review

2.1. Demographic Analysis of Applicants and Recruitment Decisions

Research conducted within Nigerian higher education institutions indicates the significant role of demographic factors in the recruitment and overall job performance of academic staff. Studies have explored how characteristics such as age, gender, educational qualifications, and professional experience can influence both the selection process and subsequent effectiveness in roles within universities (Oloruntoba & Ajayi, 2006). For example, age has been linked to variations in career commitment among librarians, with some research suggesting older employees exhibit greater commitment due to their investment in their careers (Maimuna, 2017). Similarly, gender has been examined in relation to job performance, with some studies in university libraries suggesting that male librarians may have reported higher job performance than their female counterparts, although such findings require careful consideration of potential biases and the evolving nature of work environments (Oloruntoba & Ajayi, 2006). Educational qualifications and years of work experience are generally considered positive indicators of competence and expertise in academic roles (Oginni & Afolabi, 2012). Colleges of Education, while focused on teacher training, share similarities with universities in their need for qualified academic staff, suggesting that these demographic factors likely play a comparable role in their recruitment effectiveness.

However, the system of higher education recruitment in Nigeria is also influenced by factors that extend beyond individual applicant demographics. Research has highlighted the impact of non-merit-based considerations, such as political affiliations and emphasis on local origin (indigene criteria), on recruitment decisions (Onyeaghala & Hyacinth, 2016). These factors can sometimes overshadow the importance of qualifications and experience, potentially leading to the appointment of individuals who may not be the most qualified for the positions. Such practices can undermine the overall quality of academic staff and, consequently, the standard of education provided by these institutions. Furthermore, the socio-economic status and educational background of potential students in Delta State may indirectly influence the type of staff that Colleges of Education need to recruit (Ahmad & Najeema, 2013). Understanding the challenges and backgrounds of the student population can inform the recruitment of staff who are not only academically qualified but also possess the pedagogical skills and cultural sensitivity to effectively teach and mentor a diverse student. Research indicates that parental education and socio-economic status can significantly predict students' academic achievement, suggesting that staff should be prepared to address the varying needs and preparedness levels of their students (Ahmad & Najeema, 2013).

2.2. Demand Projections and Recruitment Strategies

Nigeria, like many nations globally, faces a significant and persistent shortage of qualified teachers, particularly in certain regions and subject areas. This issue is especially pronounced in sub-Saharan Africa, where the demand for new teachers is estimated to be substantial in the coming years (Obeza, 2023). The imbalance between the supply and demand of teachers in Nigeria is further exacerbated by factors such as rapid population growth and the natural attrition of the existing teaching workforce through retirement and resignation (Aluede, Omoregie, & Aluede, 2020). Government initiatives aimed at increasing access to education, such as free education policies, have led to a surge in student enrollment, particularly at the secondary school level, further amplifying the need for qualified teachers (Oladipo, 2021). The recruitment of teachers in Nigeria's public sector is often hampered by bureaucratic processes, a lack of transparency, and, at times, inadequate funding (Oladipo, 2021). These challenges can make it difficult to attract and retain qualified individuals in the teaching profession. Moreover, enrollment trends in teacher training programs, including those offered by Colleges of Education in Delta State, play a crucial role in determining the future supply of teachers.

2.3. Recruitment Effectiveness in Colleges of Education

The effectiveness of recruitment practices in Nigerian higher institutions, including Colleges of Education, is often challenged by issues such as subjectivity in selection processes, the influence of quota systems, and instances of corruption (Ejumode, 2011). These practices can detract from the fundamental principle of merit-based recruitment, and funding which is crucial for ensuring the quality and competence of academic staff (Hohoev, 2019; Nkedishu, & Onyekwe, 2024). Having highly qualified and motivated lecturers directly impacts their ability to provide effective teacher training (Wey-Amaewhule & Umor, 2021). Therefore, adopting transparent and merit-driven recruitment processes is paramount for attracting individuals with strong academic backgrounds, relevant teaching expertise, and a genuine passion for education. To enhance recruitment effectiveness, Colleges of Education in Delta State should consider embracing modern recruitment strategies that have proven successful in other higher education system (Ezeneme, 2024). According to Ezeneme, (2024) this includes leveraging online platforms for advertising vacancies, utilizing professional networks to reach potential candidates, and implementing online application systems to

streamline the process and personalized communication with prospective applicants. When the teaching profession at all levels is perceived positively and offers opportunities for professional growth and development, it is more likely to attract talented individuals to both classroom teaching and teacher training roles (Monyamane, 2020; Ngalomba, 2022).

3. Method

The study adopted a descriptive and correlational method of the ex-post-facto research design to examine the influence of demographic analysis and job demand projections on recruitment effectiveness in Colleges of Education in Delta State. The population comprised 312 academic and senior non-academic staff involved in recruitment across the three public Colleges of Education in the state. Using stratified random sampling, a sample of 174 respondents was selected to ensure adequate representation across institutions and staff categories. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled "Demographic and Job Demand Recruitment Effectiveness Questionnaire (DJDREQ)," which included items on demographic considerations, job demand projections, and recruitment effectiveness, rated on a 5-point Likert scale. Face and content validity were established through expert review, while a pilot test conducted in a similar institution yielded a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.872, indicating high internal consistency. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and coefficient of determination for the research questions, while multiple regression analysis was employed in testing the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance, using SPSS version 26.

4. Results

Research Question 1: To what extent does the demographic analysis of applicants influence the recruitment decisions in Colleges of Education in Delta State?

Table 1 Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses on the Influence of Demographic Analysis on Recruitment Decisions

S/N	Item Description	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
1	Age, gender, and geographic background of applicants are often considered.	4.11	0.76	High
2	Demographic data help align recruitment with equity and diversity goals.	4.05	0.81	High
3	Recruitment decisions are influenced by the applicant's local government origin.	3.87	0.88	High
4	Applicant demographics are compared to institutional staffing needs.	3.95	0.83	High
5	Demographic analysis is integral to the recruitment policy framework.	4.09	0.79	High
6	Applicant socio-cultural background affects recruitment preferences.	3.91	0.84	High
7	Gender balance is factored into recruitment of academic staff.	4.10	0.70	High
8	Colleges use demographic reports to promote regional inclusion in staffing.	4.00	0.81	High
9	Records of applicant ethnicity are referenced during recruitment.	3.76	0.89	High
10	Demographic analysis supports affirmative action in recruitment.	4.08	0.75	High
Overall Mean		4.00	0.81	High

Table 1 shows mean and standard deviation of responses on the influence of demographic analysis on recruitment decisions. Result in the table revealed that respondents rated all the items high, signifying that to a large extent demographic analysis of applicants influence the recruitment decisions in Colleges of Education in Delta State with an overall mean of 4.00.

Research Question 2: How do job demand projections for staff in Delta State impact the recruitment strategies employed by Colleges of Education?

Table 2 Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses on the Impact of Job Demand Projections on Recruitment Strategies

S/N	Item Description	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
1	Job market analysis influences the number of staff recruited annually.	4.12	0.74	Agree
2	Projections for subject areas with high demand affect recruitment planning.	4.18	0.69	Agree
3	Colleges align recruitment with state government employment trends and projections.	4.06	0.78	Agree
4	Labour market projections influence the recruitment of specialists in technical fields.	4.15	0.72	Agree
5	Colleges revise their recruitment strategy based on changing job demand forecasts.	4.09	0.80	Agree
6	Demand for teachers in rural areas influences faculty recruitment strategies.	4.02	0.76	Agree
7	Shortages in specific disciplines affect how recruitment is prioritized.	4.17	0.68	Agree
8	Colleges assess national education manpower needs before recruitment.	4.04	0.73	Agree
9	There is collaboration with state education boards to understand job projections.	3.98	0.79	Agree
10	Job demand data informs recruitment adverts and job descriptions.	4.10	0.71	Agree
Overall Mean		4.09	0.74	Agree

Table 2 shows mean and standard deviation of responses on the impact of job demand projections on recruitment strategies. Result in the table revealed that respondents agree on all the items. Thus, job demand projections in Delta State significantly influence the recruitment strategies of Colleges of Education. Colleges analyze job market data, including state government employment trends and national education manpower needs, to determine the number of staff to recruit annually and prioritize recruitment in high-demand subject areas, particularly in technical fields and rural areas. This data also informs the recruitment of specialists and helps colleges align their strategies with future needs, revising them based on changing forecasts. Furthermore, collaboration with state education boards provides crucial insights into job projections, directly impacting the content of recruitment advertisements and job descriptions.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between the consideration of demographic analysis, job demand projections, and the perceived effectiveness of recruitment practices in Colleges of Education in Delta State?

Table 3 Relationship between Demographic Analysis, Job Demand Projections, and Recruitment Effectiveness

Variables	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² (%)	Remark
Demographic Analysis	4.00	0.79	0.614	0.377	37.7%	Moderate positive relationship
Job Demand Projections	4.09	0.74	0.672	0.452	45.2%	Strong positive relationship
Recruitment Effectiveness	4.02	0.81	-	-	-	Dependent variable

Table 3 shows relationship between demographic analysis, job demand projections, and recruitment effectiveness. The result revealed that there is a moderate positive relationship between demographic analysis and recruitment effectiveness ($r = 0.614$), accounting for 37.7% of the variance. A stronger positive relationship exists between job demand projections and recruitment effectiveness ($r = 0.672$), explaining 45.2% of the variance. This indicates that both variables significantly influence recruitment practices in Colleges of Education in Delta State.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the consideration of demographic analysis, job demand projections, and the perceived effectiveness of recruitment practices in Colleges of Education in Delta State.

Table 4 Multiple Regression Analysis Predicting Recruitment Effectiveness from Demographic Analysis and Job Demand Projections

Model	r	r ²	Adjusted r ²	Error of the Estimate		
1	0.643	0.413	0.433	0.449		
ANOVA Table						
Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean	F	Sig.	
Regression	41.347	2	20.673	102.42	0.000	
Residual	35.332	171	0.207			
Total	76.679	173				
Coefficients						
Predictor	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	
Constant	1.052	0.231	—	4.554	0.000	
Demographic Analysis	0.374	0.064	0.389	5.844	0.000***	
Job Demand Projections	0.421	0.061	0.434	6.889	0.000***	

***p < 0.05

Table 4 shows multiple regression analysis predicting recruitment effectiveness from demographic analysis and job demand projections. The regression model reveals a significant joint effect of demographic analysis and job demand projections on recruitment effectiveness in Colleges of Education in Delta State, with an R² of 0.413, indicating that 41.3% of the variance in recruitment effectiveness is explained by the two predictors. The ANOVA test is significant (F(2,171) = 102.42, p < 0.001), confirming that the model fits the data well. Both demographic analysis ($\beta = 0.389$, t = 5.844, p < 0.001) and job demand projections ($\beta = 0.434$, t = 6.889, p < 0.001) made statistically significant contributions. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, affirming that consideration of demographic factors and job demand projections significantly predicts recruitment effectiveness in the colleges of education.

5. Discussion

Finding revealed that to a large extent demographic analysis of applicants influence the recruitment decisions in Colleges of Education in Delta State with an overall mean of 4.00. This finding supports the findings of Kotler & Armstrong, (2001); Oloruntoba and Ajayi, (2006) who found that demographic profile of potential applicants, encompassing factors such as age, gender, experience, and qualifications, can significantly inform the development of targeted and effective recruitment strategies. The finding also supports Maimuna, (2017) whose finding highlighted how demographic factors such as age have been linked to career commitment, with older employees often exhibiting greater commitment due to their career investment. The finding further supports Oginni and Afolabi, (2012) who found that educational qualifications and years of work experience are generally considered positive indicators of competence and expertise in academic roles. However, while this finding demonstrates the positive influence of demographic analysis, it is important to note the cautionary perspective raised by Onyeaghala & Hyacinth, (2016) who highlighted the potential impact of non-merit-based considerations, such as political affiliations and emphasis on local origin (indigene criteria), on recruitment decisions within Nigerian universities. This suggests that while demographic analysis is highly influential in recruitment decisions, institutions must ensure that such analysis focuses on merit-based demographic factors that enhance recruitment effectiveness rather than potentially discriminatory characteristics that could undermine the quality of academic staff.

Finding revealed that job demand projections in Delta State significantly influence the recruitment strategies of Colleges of Education. Colleges analyze job market data, including state government employment trends and national education manpower needs, to determine the number of staff to recruit annually and prioritize recruitment in high-demand subject areas, particularly in technical fields and rural areas. This data also informs the recruitment of specialists and helps colleges align their strategies with future needs, revising them based on changing forecasts. Furthermore, collaboration with state education boards provides crucial insights into job projections, directly impacting the content of recruitment advertisements and job descriptions. This finding is in agreement with Ejumode, (2011) who discovered

that aligning recruitment efforts with these projections ensures that colleges are recruiting faculty who can effectively train teachers in high-need areas, thereby contributing to meeting the overall educational demands of Delta State. The finding also supports Oladipo, (2021) who discovered that understanding job demand projections is essential for institutions to strategically plan programmes and staff recruitment, particularly in anticipating future needs in specific subject areas such as science, mathematics, and technical and vocational education. This demonstrates the importance of analyzing job market data by highlighting how government initiatives like free education policies have led to increased student enrollment, amplifying the need for qualified teachers. The finding further aligns with Obeza (2023) and Aluede, Omoregie, & Aluede, (2020) who noted that Nigeria faces significant teacher shortages, particularly in certain regions and subject areas, with the imbalance between supply and demand being exacerbated by factors such as rapid population growth and natural attrition of the existing teaching workforce through retirement and resignation.

Finding revealed that there is a significant relationship between the consideration of demographic analysis, job demand projections, and the perceived effectiveness of recruitment practices in Colleges of Education in Delta State. This finding is in accordance with the findings of Oloruntoba & Ajayi, (2006) who established that demographic analysis can reveal trends within the applicant pool, allowing institutions to tailor their outreach efforts, while job demand projections help ensure that colleges recruit faculty who can effectively address future educational needs. The finding also supports the assertion by Carver-Thomas & Darling-Hammond, (2019) that aligning recruitment efforts with job demand projections ensures that colleges are recruiting faculty who can effectively train teachers in high-need areas. Furthermore, this finding validates the theoretical framework suggested by Ekwoaba, Ikeije, & Ufoma, (2015) that this proactive approach not only addresses potential teacher shortages but can also inform the enrollment and program offerings of the Colleges of Education themselves. However, it is important to acknowledge that while this significant relationship exists, the effectiveness may be moderated by systemic challenges in Nigerian higher education recruitment, including bureaucratic processes, lack of transparency, and instances of corruption as highlighted by Ejumode, (2011) and Hohoev, (2019). Despite these potential constraints, the significant relationship found in this study demonstrates that strategic consideration of both demographic factors and job demand projections can enhance recruitment effectiveness in Colleges of Education, directly impacting the quality of teacher training and subsequently influencing educational experiences throughout Delta State.

6. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that recruitment effectiveness in Colleges of Education in Delta State is significantly influenced by the strategic use of demographic analysis and job demand projections. The consideration of applicants' demographic profiles such as age, gender, ethnicity, and local origin plays a vital role in guiding recruitment decisions to promote equity, diversity, and regional inclusion. In addition, job demand projections strongly shape recruitment strategies, as Colleges of Education align their staffing needs with labor market forecasts, government employment trends, and subject area shortages. This forward-looking approach enables institutions to prioritize critical disciplines, especially in technical and rural teaching fields, thereby enhancing the responsiveness and relevance of recruitment efforts. Furthermore, the significant positive relationship between these variables and recruitment effectiveness underscores the importance of data-driven planning. Consequently, institutions that integrate demographic and labor market analyses into their recruitment frameworks are better positioned to make informed, equitable, and future-ready staffing decisions.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

- Colleges of Education should formalize the use of demographic data and job demand projections in their recruitment policies to ensure equitable and strategically aligned hiring practices.
- Management should partner with state education boards and labor market analysts to regularly access updated job demand forecasts, ensuring recruitment meets current and future workforce needs.
- Recruitment efforts should be directed toward disciplines with documented shortages, especially technical and rural teaching fields, to bridge critical staffing gaps.
- Recruitment frameworks should be reviewed regularly to reflect evolving demographic trends and labor market dynamics, enabling responsive and adaptive staffing strategies.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Ahmad, S., & Najeema, M. (2013). Influence of parental education on academic achievement of students. *International Journal of Educational Planning & Administration*, 3(2), 177-184.
- [2] Aluede, O. O., Omoregie, E. O., & Aluede, O. R. (2020). Deterioration of Nigeria's secondary education system: Causes and consequences. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(1), 108-114.
- [3] Carver-Thomas, L., & Darling-Hammond, L. (2019). The elusive quest for equity: Evidence on equal opportunity in out-of-field teaching. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 27, 12.
- [4] Ejumode, O. (2011). Recruitment and selection of staff in Nigerian universities: Challenges and prospects. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(22), 9012-9018.
- [5] Ekwoaba, J. O., Ikeije, U. U., & Ufoma, N. (2015). The impact of recruitment and selection criteria on organizational performance. *British Journal of Marketing Studies*, 3(3), 33-49.
- [6] Ezeneme, E. V., (2024) Digitalization of the recruitment and selection of academic staff of colleges of education in Nigeria. *Journal of Association of Educational Management and Policy Practitioners (JA'EMPP)*. 6(2), 335-342
- [7] Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2013). National Policy on Education (6th ed.). Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC).
- [8] Hohoev, S. (2019). Impact of staff recruitment on lecturers' teaching effectiveness in federal colleges of education in North Eastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Recent Research in Social Sciences and Humanities (IJRSSSH)*, 6(2), 1-9.
- [9] Kotler, P., & Armstrong, G. (2001). *Principles of marketing*. Prentice Hall.
- [10] Maimuna, S. O. (2017). Recruitment and selection criteria as predictors of academic staff job performance in state-owned universities in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research/Social and Management Sciences*, 3(1), 1-16.
- [11] Monyamane, M. (2020). The impact of promotion on employee motivation and job satisfaction: A case of selected retail stores in Lesotho. *Journal of Human Resource Management*, 8(1), 1-10.
- [12] Ngalomba, J. (2022). The effect of promotion on employee performance in selected government ministries in Zambia. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 17(1), 1-12.
- [13] Nkedishu V.C., Nwaorgu, E. H., Egwunyenga, E. J., (2022). Instructors' Proficiency and Employment of ICT in Teaching through Emerging Technologies and Innovations in Delta State Government Secondary Schools. *Innovations*. 70(3) 506-517. <https://journal-innovations.com/assets/uploads/doc/1567b-506-517.20062.pdf>
- [14] Nkedishu, V. C., & Onyekwe, E. C. (2024). Funding patterns and financial management practices in public and private secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Education Humanities and Commerce*, 05(01), 178-190. <https://doi.org/10.37602/IJREHC.2024.5115>.
- [15] Nkedishu, V. C. (2020). Workers Job Security and Productivity in Missionary Educational Centres in Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 9(4). <https://ijarped.com/index.php/journal/article/view/2287>
- [16] Nkedishu, V. C., (2022). Administrative Efficiencies and Teachers Productivity in Delta State Secondary Schools, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 26(3), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2022/v26i330627>
- [17] Obeza, E. L. (2023). The Quality of Educational Development in Nigeria. *Educational Research*, 14(2) 1-3. <https://www.interestjournals.org/articles/the-quality-of-educational-development-in-nigeria-96573.html>
- [18] Oginni, B. O., & Afolabi, O. A. (2012). Recruitment and selection practices in the Nigerian labour market: An exploratory study. *Journal of Human Resource Management*, 2012, 1-8.

- [19] Okwelle, P. C., & Deebom, T. M. (2009). Lecturer Quality, Quantity and Gender in Colleges of Education in Nigeria. *College Student Journal*, 43(2), 445-454.
- [20] Oladipo, O. O. (2021). Teacher recruitment and selection in Nigeria: Challenges and the way forward. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(3), 1-8.
- [21] Olorunfoba, S. O., & Ajayi, N. A. (2006). Demographic factors and job performance of librarians in Nigerian universities. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 9(1), 1-10.
- [22] Onyeaghala, U. J., & Hyacinth, O. (2016). Recruitment and selection practices in tertiary institutions in Nigeria: The case of Imo State University. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 6(11), 308-321.
- [23] Wey-Amaewhule, B. B., & Umor, U. M. (2021). Staff promotion and lecturers' instructional delivery in universities in Rivers State. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Review*, 12(1), 1-10.